

EUROAGEISM AND ROBERT GORDON UNIVERESITY

WHAT IS AGEISM?

ONLINE WEBINAR: AGEISM IN WORKFORCEE

Why ageism concerns us all and how we can combat it!

ONLINE WORKSHOP - 06 ARPIL 2021. 14H00 CET

REGISTER HERE: <https://www.rgu.ac.uk/events>

ONLINE WEBINAR: AGEISM IN WORKFORCE

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Stefan Hopf, Lola Casal-Sánchez**

Employers often have negative attitudes towards older workers. Age discrimination persists even though older workers are not necessarily less healthy, less educated, less skilful or productive than their younger counterpart. This webinar provides an in-depth understanding of ageism in the workforce and presents tools to combat it and increase opportunities for intergenerational teams, and introducing campaigns to challenge the myths and inaccurate stereotypes that hinder older people's ability to participate.

For more information about EuroAgeism, please visit <https://euroageism.eu/>. You may also email us at info@euroageism.eu

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